

Transcriptomics analysis in the ZERO Childhood Cancer Program

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ZERO Childhood Cancer Program

Australia's most comprehensive precision medicine program for children with cancer

Zero2 Cohort

- Cohort 1 - High risk cancer
- Cohort 3 - Non-high risk primary CNS
- Cohort 2 - Rare Cancer
- Cohort 6 - Non-high risk acute lymphoblastic leukaemia
- Cohort 8 - Non-high risk sarcoma
- Cohort 7 - Non-high risk lymphoma
- Cohort 12 - Other non-high risk tumours
- Cohort 4B - Non-high risk neuroblastoma
- Cohort 9 - Non-high risk renal tumours
- Cohort 4A - High risk neuroblastoma
- Cohort 11 - Non-high risk thyroid and endocrine
- Cohort 5 - Non-high risk acute myeloid leukaemia
- Cohort 10 - Non-high risk hepatic and biliary tree
- Cohort 13 - Germline only

National Precision Medicine Program

CLINICAL DATA

TARGET,
PRISM,
ZERO2

GENOMIC DATA

WGS RNAseq

methylation

>130M
variants
analysed

BIOLOGICAL MODEL DATA

PDX HTS Drugs

>200 cancer
models
established

>160
curated drug
screens

Up to
150
drugs

BIOSPECIMENS

>3000 tumour
samples
>1500 germline
samples

As of 7/3/2024

1439
unique patients

Cancer
diagnosis/prognosis
clinical information

Genetic variants

>5000 genetic
variants
identified

Public annotation

Integration API

Published data

National MTB

Investigator Initiated Trials
Clinical Research Reporting
Advanced and Emerging
Novel Research Programs

Significant infrastructure and systems upgrades, customised pipelines and software platforms to support large scale genomic precision medicine nationally

New benchmark transforming diagnosis and management

Comprehensive Automated RNA-seq pipeline: Carbonite

~300 SU – per patient

Compatible:

- hg19 and hg38
- Processed >1200 patient samples

nextflow

COMMON
WORKFLOW
LANGUAGE

Fusions

Structural Rearrangements

SNVs/InDels

Gene Expression

Isoforms – Splicing

Transposable Elements

Immunoprofiling

*Angela Lin

Research & Development to improve patient care

Constant accumulation of patient samples (~20 per week) provides us with a unique and comprehensive resource to further advance our knowledge of paediatric cancer to:

- Improve outcome through novel therapies
- Identify novel mechanisms that drive disease
- Provide targeted treatment options
- Detect high-risk disease and chance of relapse at diagnosis

Key areas of research:

- Pipeline improvements to increase the clinical utility of RNA-seq data
- Immunoprofiling paediatric cancer
 - New clinical trial opening for personalised immunotherapy in paediatric patients
- Expression analysis for molecular diagnostic classifications
- Functional interpretation of DNA variants
 - Allele specific expression
 - Alternate splicing

